

The effect of Employee's Performance Quality on the Services Improvement of Hajj and Umrah

(A Study at the Division of Hajj and Umrah, Regional Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera Regency, Indonesia)

Muzakir Ahmad¹, Saiful Deni², Muhammad Husni Arifin³, Lisda Ariani Simabur⁴.

^{1,3,4} Faculty of Law, Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

² Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This paper aims to discuss the quality of employee's performances in the implementation of Hajj and Umrah, and to explore and reveal the advantages and disadvantages on service improvement for Hajj and Umrah pilgrims to answer the need for qualified public services in the division of Hajj and Umrah, the regional Ministry of Religion of West Halmahera Regency as from the mandate of the regulations and legislation by examining the independent variables including the quality of human resources, budget, the use of Integrated Information and Computerization System of Hajj (SISKOHAT) facilities, and work culture towards the Dependent Variable of improving the quality of Hajj and Umrah Services. The data was processed through questionnaires which were distributed directly to all respondents. The sampling technique was the Simple Random Sampling technique. Through this variable approach, this research was elaborated logically factual so that it could be described by descriptive analysis. There were 20 Hajj and Umrah pilgrims as the sample out of 103 population. The data analysis method in this research was multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 21 to process the data. The results showed the regression equation $Y = -6.605 + 1.965X_1 + 1.433X_2 - 0.525X_3 + 0.606$ where the coefficient of the independent variable has a positive influence on the dependent variable except for the Siskohat variable. The partial analysis showed that the t-test of Human Resources Quality was (1.965), Budget Variable was (1.433), the use of Siskohat was (-0.525), Work Culture was (0.606) which was bigger than (>) the t-table (0.004 is smaller than 0.05) then H_0 was rejected so it could be concluded that there was a partial effect on the services of the Hajj Pilgrims, while the results of Simultaneous analysis using the F-test, it was obtained that the F-test was (38.635) > F-table (2.90) or Sig. (0.00) < 0.05 then the H_a was accepted H_0 is rejected. Then it can be concluded that the Quality of Human Resources, Budget, Siskohat Facilities, and Simultaneous Work Culture (Test F) has a positive effect on increasing the employee's performances on Hajj Pilgrims Services in the division of Hajj and Umrah at the Ministry of Religion office, West Halmahera Regency.

KEYWORDS –Quality of Employee's Performances, Service Improvement, Pilgrims of Hajj and Umrah.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the functions of government in the religious affairs is to organize the Hajj and Umrah (minor Hajj). This service mandate is based on the constitution number 8 of 2019 which aims at providing guidance, service, and protection for Hajj and Umrah pilgrims so they can perform their worship in accordance with the provisions of Islamic law and realize independence and resilience in organizing the Hajj and Umrah. The constitution emphasizes that the government is obliged to carry out the Hajj through guidance, service, and

protection by providing facilities, convenience, security, and comfort needed by every citizen in performing the Hajj. The worship, which involves thousands of worshippers from all over Indonesia, is classified as a national task as well as a government responsibility under the supervision of Ministry of Religion. For this reason, the Government through the Ministry of Religion will continue to strive to improve the management system to improve the quality of services for Hajj and Umrah pilgrims by carrying out new innovations according to the dynamics and demands of changes occurred.

Domestically, the process of organizing the Hajj encounters some serious problems, especially the organizers at the ministerial levels, both the Provincial and Regional Ministry of Religion, particularly at of the Ministry of Religion office of West Halmahera Regency. These problems vary from administration services, infrastructure (*Siskohat* app), budget, as well as work culture and other public services. These services need to be improved because they play an important role to realize better services in organizing the Hajj and Umrah.

This study, therefore, aimed at exploring the effect of employee's performance quality on the services improvement of hajj and umrah at regional Ministry of Religion office, West Halmahera Regency. This study was also to answer the following questions:

1. Does the availability of human resources (X1), limited budget (X2), *Siskohat* facility (X3), and work culture factors (X4) have a partial effect on improving the performance of the employees in the division of Hajj and Umrah at regional Ministry of Religion West Halmahera Regency?
2. Does the availability of human resources (X1), limited budget (X2), *Siskohat* facility (X3), and work culture factors (X4) simultaneously improve the performance of the employees in the division of Hajj and Umrah at regional Ministry of Religion West Halmahera Regency?
3. Does the improvement of performance quality of the employees have a positive and significant impact on the service system of Hajj and *Umrah* pilgrims?

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Public services basically involve very broad aspects of life. Government, as the highest policy maker, has the function of providing various public services needed by the community, ranging from regulation services to other services to meet the needs of the society in education, health, and, etc. In fact, the current service is still less than expected because there are still many problems related to the quality of public services.

Various problems that occur in government as the public services agencies, precisely in the Hajj and Umrah division of Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera, increasingly make people less confident in the quality of services provided by the government. To find out the extent to which the quality of public services carried out in the Hajj and Umrah division, it is necessary to carry out an in-depth analysis by measuring service quality which includes Physical Evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Guarantee, and Empathy.

Referring to the description, the researcher employs a theory that explains the approach measuring the service quality includes tangible facts with the appearance of employees, comfort, discipline, and ease of access to customers, reliability with accuracy, standard of ability and expertise in using mini-regulations, responsiveness with speed, accuracy, accuracy in service, as well as empathy in understanding the desired wants and needs.

2.2 Operational Definitions

2.1.1 Performance Concept

Performance is a description of the achievement level of the implementation of an activity/program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives, vision, and mission of the organization contained on the strategic planning of an organization. The term performance is often used to refer to the achievement

or level of success of individuals or groups.

According to Achmad S.Ruky, there are several indicators in improving performances, through appraisal performance, which is: a). a means to find out/map the competencies possessed by employees. b) carried out as a basis for fostering employee performance, c) a means of motivating employees to improve job performance

2.1.2 Human Resource Management

Management by G. R. Terry quoted in the book "Management, Basics, Understanding and Problems" (2011:2) states that: "*Management is a distinctive process consisting of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling actions carried out to determine and achieve the goals set determined using human resources and other resources.*"

2.1.3 Budget

M. Nafarin (2007: 11) states that "budget is a quantitative plan (an amount) periodically compiled based on a program that has been approved. Budget is a written plan regarding the activities of an organization which is stated quantitatively for a certain period and is expressed in units of money but also expressed in terms of units of goods and services."

Based on the constitution no. 34 of 2014 provides its own enlightenment for the management and development of hajj funds in accordance with the sharia economic and financial system

2.1.4 Integrated Information and Computerized Systems of Hajj(SISKOHAT)

"O,nrian JA" states that information system is an organized combination of people, hardware, software, communication networks, and data resources to collect and disseminate information within an organization. An information system can be likened to as a collection of people or data users and procedures that work together to achieve the same goal.

2.1.5 Organizational Work Culture

Martins N. Martins (2013:380) defines organizational culture as "*a system of share meaning held by members distinguishing the organization from other organizations*". Means held by members who distinguish one organization from another, this definition shows that organizational culture distinguishes one organization from another.

2.1.6 The Concept of Public Service Quality

According to Hardiyansyah (2011:12), the notion of public service means serving the needs of people or communities or organizations that have an interest in the organization, in accordance with the basic rules and procedures determined and aimed at providing satisfaction to service recipients.

2.3 Hypotheses

Based on the research background, the hypotheses are as follows:

H_0 = There is no partially significant effect between Human Resources (X1), Budget (X2), *SISKOHAT* (X3), and Work Culture (X4) on Service Improvement (Y).

H_a = There is partially a significant effect between the variables of Human Resources (X1), Budget (X2), *SISKOHAT* (X3), and Work Culture (X4) on Service Improvement (Y). Where the hypothesis criteria for acceptance are as follows:

If t-value > t-table or sig. < 0.05, then the H_0 is rejected, and the H_a is accepted.

If t-value < t-table or sig. > 0.05, then the H_0 is accepted, and the H_a is rejected.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research design

Research design is a plan on how to carry out research. It is a way of collecting and analyzing data so that it can be carried out effectively and in accordance with the research objectives. The research design provided a clear guide for researchers in conducting their research¹. This study was conducted at the Regional Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera Regency. There were 20 prospective Hajj Pilgrims became the sample which was taken by doing simple random sampling. Simple random sampling was taken because the prospective Hajj and Umrah pilgrims were considered as homogeneous as they were the prospective Hajj and Umrah pilgrims in 2019 under the division of the Hajj and Umrah, Regional Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera Regency.

3.2 Data Analysis Method

3.2.1 Multiple linear regression analysis of the variables

The purpose of this analysis is to determine the effect between Human Resources (X1), Budget (X2), SISKOHAT (X3), Work Culture (X4) on the dependent variable, using linear regression equations as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + e$$

where:

a = Variable / constant number

b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4 = Regression Coefficient

X = independent variable, consisted of:

X_1 = Human Resources (HR)

X_2 = Budget

X_3 = SISKOHAT

X_4 = Work Culture

e = Other variables

Y = Dependent variable

To get the value of a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 an SPSS program was used. This was done to obtain a valid result and minimize the risk of miscalculation.

3.2.2 T Test

The t-test is used to test the truth of the hypothesis individually between the independent variables and the dependent variable. This test aims to test the partial effect of the dependent variable by comparing the t-table and t-value. Each result is then compared with the t table obtained using an error level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (df) = nk. The following is the partial t-test formula (Sugiyono, 2013):

$$\frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

where:

r = correlation coefficient

n = number of data

r^2 = coefficient of determination

t = t value

3.2.3 F Test

The F test analysis was used to determine the joint effect of the independent variables on the independent variables.

The steps for testing the hypothesis are as follows:

- a. Determine F value

Formula F value:

$$F_{\text{value}} = \frac{r^2/k}{(1-r^2)/(n-k-1)} = \frac{r^2(n-k-1)}{(1-r^2)} = \frac{r^r(k-1)}{(n-k)(1-r^2)}$$

where:

F = Fischer probability distribution
 r = multiple correlation coefficient
 k = number of independent variables
 n = number of samples

- b. Determine the F table

F-Test Table for $\alpha = 5\%$ with the numerator degrees of freedom (df1) = $k-1$ and for the denominator (df2) = nk

- c. Test Criteria

- a) If the F-value < F-table or the sig. > 0.05 then H_0 is accepted, and H_a is rejected
- b) If the F-value > F-table or sig. < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted

3.2.4 Co efficient of Determination

This analysis was used to determine how much contribution the independent variable affected the dependent variable. The formula is as follows:

$$R^2 = \frac{b_1 \sum x_1y + b_2 \sum x_2y + b_3 \sum x_3y + b_4 \sum x_4y + e}{Y^2}$$

where:

R^2 = Coefficient of Determination

b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4 = Regression Coefficient

X = independent variable, consisted of:

X_1 = Human Resources

X_2 = Budget

X_3 = SISKOHAT

X_4 = Work Culture

e = Other variables

Y = Independent variable (Service Improvement)

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Respondent Data

From the 20 respondents who filled out the questionnaire, the data showing the number of Hajj/Umrah pilgrims according to the gender were as follows:

Table 4.1. Number of Hajj/Umrah Pilgrims by gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid man	11	55.0	55.0	55.0
Woman	9	45.0	45.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	100.0	

4.1.2 Results of Respondents' Attitudes toward Services (X_1)

Table 4.2. Respondents Attitudes Towards Services

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Good	10	50.0	50.0	50.0
Very good	10	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	100.0	

From the results of the table above in question no. 1 it was found that the respondents only filled out the questionnaire on the attitude of "very good and good".

4.1.3 Results of Respondents' Attitudes towards Satisfaction (Y)

Table 4.3. Respondents Attitudes Towards Satisfaction

No	Respondent's Attitude	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Very satisfied	8	40.0
2	Satisfied	12	60.0
3	Somewhat satisfied	-	-
4	Not satisfied	-	-
5	Very Dissatisfied	-	-
Total		20	100

From the results of the table above in question no. 1 it was found that respondents only filled out the questionnaire on the attitude of "very satisfied and satisfied".

4.1.4 Statistical Analysis Based on Total Respondents' Answers and Its Relationship with the Level of Significance

Table 4.4. Statistics Analysis

	TX1	TX2	TX3	TX4	TY1	TY2	TY3	YT4
N Valid	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
mean	35.40	38.75	21.35	26.75	35.15	38.95	21.10	26.65
Variance	6.884	15,987	3,292	7.776	9.187	14,261	3.042	8,661
Range	8	11	8	10	9	10	6	7
Minimum	32	34	17	20	31	35	19	23
Maximum	40	45	25	30	40	45	25	30

Of the total respondent's answers as many as 28 questions on all variables, the lowest average answer is in the Quality of Performance (X), on T(X3) which is SISKOHAT. The respondents only provide an average value of 21.35 answers, and on Service (Satisfaction) T (Y3) which only gives an average value of 21, 10.

4.1.5 Validity and Reliability Test Results

A. Validity test

The validity test was carried out to determine whether the questions were valid or not, where the entire research variable contained 28 questions that the respondents had to answer based on calculations using SPSS21 Software.

B. Reliability Test

After the validity test was carried out, then the reliability test was carried out on the items that have been valid. The reliability test was used to determine the level of consistency of fixed answers to be tested whenever the instrument is presented.

The reliability test was done using *Cronbach's Alpha* formula with the help of *SPSS 21 Software*. The results are in the following table.

Table 4.4. Reliability Test of Variable X (performance quality)

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,921	28

Table 4.5 Variable Y Reliability Test (Service Improvement)

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,935	28

Based on the reliability test on the quality of performance and service improvement, it showed that the results were reliable. It means that the instrument can be trusted or relied on. This means that the measurement results of the question for this study were relatively stable. This was because it is in accordance with the reliability criteria where *Cronbach's Alpha value is* > 0.60 (Ghozali, 2007:42). The results of the performance reliability test and Service Improvement using *SPSS* can be seen below.

4.1.6 Data analysis

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The purpose of this analysis was to determine the effect between Human Resources (X_1), Budget (X_2), SISKOHAT(X_3), Work Culture (X_4) and the dependent variable which is the Hajj pilgrims Services in West Halmahera.

Multiple linear regression equations for the independent variables that affect Hajj Pilgrim Services are as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + e$$

From the results of calculations using *SPSS 21*, the multiple linear regression equation obtained is:

$$Y = -6,605 + 1,965X_1 + 1,433X_2 - 0,525X_3 + 0,606$$

Interpretation:

a. Constant coefficient

The constant value is 6.605, which means that the constant is negative, indicating that if there are no independent variables consisting of HR variables (X_1), Budget (X_2), SISKOHAT (X_3), Work Culture (X_4), then there is no Service Improvement (Y), thus it can be seen that the Service (Y) is not only influenced by the independent variables in this study.

b. HR coefficient (b_1)

The HR regression coefficient (b_1) is 1.965 with a significant value of 0.004 (smaller than 0.05) which means that the HR variable (X_1) has a significant effect on services (Y), at an error level of 5%. P-value of 0.004 indicates that the risk of decision-making errors then it states that there is a 0% effect of the HR variable (X_1) on Service (Y). The positive regression coefficient of 1.965 explains that if the increase in the HR variable (X_1) is 1 unit, the service increases for 1.965 units. This means that the better the human resources, the better the service is.

c. Budget Coefficient (b_2)

Budget regression coefficient (b_2) is 1.433 with a significant value of 0.004 (smaller than 0.05) which means that the Budget variable (X_2) has a significant effect on services at an error level of 5%. P-value of 0.000 indicates that the risk of decision-making errors then it states that there is a 0% effect of the Budget variable (X_2) on Service Improvement (Y). The positive regression coefficient of 1.433 explains that if the increase in the Budget variable (X_2) is 1 unit, the Service will experience an increase of 1.433 units. This means that the better the budget is, the better the service is.

d. SISKOHAT coefficient (b_3)

The regression coefficient for SISKOHAT (b_3) is -0.525 with a significant value of 0.456 (greater than 0.05) which means that the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) has no significant effect on service improvement. The P-value of 0.456 indicates that the risk of decision-making which means the effect of the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) on the Service (Y) is 45.6%. The negative regression coefficient of 0.456 explains that if the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) increases by 1 unit, then the service decreases by 0.456 units. This means that if the SISKOHAT service decreases, the service will also decrease.

e. Coefficient of Work Culture (b_4)

The regression coefficient of Work Culture (b_3) is 0.606 with a significant value of 0.400 (greater than 0.05) which means that the Work Culture variable (X_4) has a significant effect on service improvement. P-value of 40% indicates that the risk of decision-making errors which means that the effect of Work Culture variable (X_3) on Service (Y) is 40%. Thus, if the work culture is improved, it will greatly affect the improvement of Hajj services.

T test (Partial Test)

The t-test was used to determine the significant level of each independent variable on the dependent. In other words, it was to know how far the influence of an individual independent variable in explaining the variation of the dependent variable by examining a t-test with a t-table or a t-value probability with a significant level (5%) with the following hypothetical formula:

H_0 = There is partially no significant effect between HR variables (X_1), Budget (X_2), SISKOHAT (X_3), Work Culture (X_4), on Service (Y).

H_a = There is partially a significant influence between HR variables (X_1), Budget (X_2), SISKOHAT (X_3), Work Culture (X_4) on service (Y).

Based on the SPSS test results, it was obtained that:

Table 4.6. F-value test results

ANOVA(b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2033,566	4	508,392	38,635	,000(a)
	Residual	197.384	15	13,159		
	Total	2230,950	19			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Culture, SISKOHAT, Human Resources, budget
- b. Dependent Variable: Service Improvement

Based on the results of the table above, it shows that the F-value (38.635) > F-table (2.90) or the value of Sig. (0.00) < 0.05 then H_a is accepted, and H_0 is rejected. This shows that there is a significant effect of Human Resources (X_1), Budget (X_2), SISKOHAT (X_3), Work Culture (X_4) on the Service (Y).

4.2 Discussion

From the description and results above, the author was able discuss or describe four variables that affect the quality of employee's performances on improving the quality of services for Hajj and Umrah in the division of Hajj and Umrah of the regional Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera Regency. The four variables were:

1) Variable Quality of Human Resources (HR) (X_1)

The HR regression coefficient (b_1) is 1.965 with a significant value of 0.004 (smaller than 0.05) which means that the HR variable (X_1) has a significant effect on services (Y), at an error level of 5%. P-value of 0.004 indicates that the risk of decision-making errors then it states that there is a 0% effect of the HR variable (X_1) on Service(Y). The positive regression coefficient of 1.965 explains that if the increase in the HR variable (X_1) is 1 unit, the service increases for 1.965 units. This means that the better the human resources, the better the service is.

2) Budget Variable (X_2)

Budget regression coefficient (b_2) is 1.433 with a significant value of 0.004 (smaller than 0.05) which means that the Budget variable (X_2) has a significant effect on services at an error level of 5%. P-value of 0.000 indicates that the risk of decision-making errors then it states that there is a 0% effect of the Budget variable (X_2) on Service Improvement (Y). The positive regression coefficient of 1.433 explains that if the increase in the Budget variable (X_2) is 1 unit, the Service will experience an

increase of 1.433 units. This means that the better the budget is, the better the service is.

3) Variable SISKOHAT (X_3)

The regression coefficient for SISKOHAT (b_3) is -0.525 with a significant value of 0.456 (greater than 0.05) which means that the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) has no significant effect on service improvement. The P-value of 0.456 indicates that the risk of decision-making which means the effect of the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) on the Service (Y) is 45.6%. The negative regression coefficient of 0.456 explains that if the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) increases by 1 unit, then the service decreases by 0.456 units. This means that if the SISKOHAT service decreases, the service will also decrease.

4) Work Culture Variable (X_4)

The regression coefficient of Work Culture (b_4) is 0.606 with a significant value of 0.400 (greater than 0.05) which means that the Work Culture variable (X_4) has a significant effect on service improvement. P-value of 40% indicates that the risk of decision-making errors which means that the effect of Work Culture variable (X_4) on Service (Y) is 40%. Thus, if the work culture is improved, it will greatly affect the improvement of Hajj services.

The research has four variables: Human Resources Variable (X_1), Budget Variable (X_2), *Siskohat* Facilities Variable (X_3), and Work Culture Variable (X_4) in the division of Hajj and Umrah at the Ministry of Religion, West Halmahera Regency. If it is better, then it has a very positive and significant effect on the quality of the Hajj and Umrah division itself. The *Siskohat* variable (X_3) did not significantly affect the improvement of Hajj and Umrah services (Y), but the HR Variable (X_1), the Budget Variable (X_2), *Siskohat* Facility Variable (X_3), and Work Culture Variable (X_4) had a linear relationship and had a strong effect and mutually support one another to encourage the quality of quality of Hajj services (Y) starting from the registration process, documents, the coaching process, departure, and the pilgrimage in Saudi Arabia to repatriation in the country.

V. CONCLUSION

1. The linear regression $Y = -6,605 + 1,965 X_1 + 1,433X_2 - 0,525X_3 + 0,606X_4$ showed that the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) had a negative regression coefficient (b_3) of -0.525, explaining that if the SISKOHAT variable (X_3) was increased by 1 unit, it would decrease by 0.525 units. Meanwhile, for the significant level value, it was obtained that the value X_3 did not have a significant effect on service (Y).
2. The results of the t-test showed that the t-value X_1 (3.411) > t-table (2.704), t-count X_2 (3.359) > t-table (2.704), t-count X_3 (-0.766) < t-table (2.704), t-count X_4 (0.866) > t-table (2.704). It can be concluded that the variable X_3 has no significant effect on congregational services (Y). Because the t-value < t-table, while for variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , X_4 , partially had significant effect on Service (Y).
3. The results of the F test showed that the four variables (X) had a significant effect on service (Y). This was because the F-value (38.635) > F-table (3.24).

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abdul Kadir, *Pengenalan Sistem Informasi*, Yogyakarta: Publisher Andi, 2003
- [2.] Andrew F. Sikula, "Manajemen, Dasar, Pengertian Dan Masalah" 2011
- [3.] Alwi. Syafarudin, *Transformasi Pelayanan Publik*, Pembaruan, Yogyakarta. 2001

-
- [4.] A. Sihontang, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cet.1, Publisher, PT. Pradnya Paramita, Jakarta. 2007
- [5.] Alexander, Abe, *Perencanaan Daerah Memperkuat Prakarsa Rakyat Dalam Otonomi Daerah*. LAPERA Pustaka Utama Yogyakarta. Hal. 2001
- [6.] Alwi, Syarifudin, *Transformasi Pelayanan Publik*, Pembaruan, Yogyakarta. 2001
- [7.] Anwar, Saiful, *Dasar – Dasar Prilaku Organisasi*, UII Pres, Yogyakarta. 2002.
- [8.] Andreas Lako, *Kepemimpinan dan Kinerja Organisasi* (Yogyakarta, Amara Books)
- [9.] Basyuni, Muhammad Maftuh. .” *Reformasi Manajemen Haji*. “Jakarta FDK. Press.2008
- [10.] Burhanudin, *Analisis Administrasi Manajemen dan Kepemimpinan Pendidikan*, Penerbit Bumi Aksara, Jakarta 1994
- [11.] Chand`ler & Plano “*Teori Administrasi Publik*” 2007
- [12.] Desler, Garry 2000. *Human Resource Management* (Indonesian Edition) Part 1. Prehalindo, Jakarta.
- [13.] Dwiyanto, dkk. *Reformasi Birokrasi Publik Di Indonesia*, PSKK. UGM, Yogyakarta. 2001
- [14.] Deni, Saiful, *Dinamika Birokrasi Pelayanan Publik*, CV, Grafika Indah, Yogyakarta. 2005
- [15.] Gunaydin S. dan K. MC Cusker, *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*, 2015
- [16.] Gary Yukil, *Kepemimpinan Dalam Organisasi* (Jakarta : PT. Indeks, 2005)
- [17.] Gibson, James, L. John M, Ivancevich dan James H. Donnelly, Jr., 1996 ; *Organisasi : Perilaku, Struktur, Proses*, Binarupa Aksara, Part I, Translated by: Nunuk Adiarni, Eighth Edition, Jakarta
- [18.] Goetsch dan Davis “*Kualitas Pelayanan Publik*” , 2011
- [19.] Terry G.R., “*Manajemen, Dasar, Pengertian Dan Masalah* ” 2011
- [20.] Harbani, Pasalong, 2000, *Teoiri Administrasi Publik*, Penerbit : Cv, Alfabeta, Bandung.
- [21.] Hardiyansyah “*Pengertian Pelayanan Public*” Jogjakarta : Gava Media (2011: 12)
- [22.] H. Hadari, Nawawi, *Manajemen Strategik Organisasi Non Profit Bidang Pemerintahan*, (UGM) Gadjah Mada University Press. 2003
- [23.] -----, *Metode Penelitian Bidang Sosial* , Gadjah Mada Universty Press, Yogyakarta . 2005 Hadi Sutrisno *Unsur – Unsur Pokok Metode Penelitian Ilmiah*, DIKTI, Jakarta, 1990.
- [24.] Henry Simomora, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Second Edition. Yogyakarta . STIE YKPN. 2004
- [25.] Hadi Sutrisno, *Unsur – Unsur Pokok Metode Penelitian Ilmiah*, DIKTI, Jakarta, 1990. Harbani, Pasalong, *Teoiri Administrasi Publik*, Penerbit : CV, Alfabeta, Bandung. 2000

-
- [26.] Harold Koontz dan Cyrill O'Donnel, "*Manajemen, Dasar, Pengertian Dan Masalah*" 2011
- [27.] Ibrahim Amir "*Teori dan Kosep Pelayanan Publik dan implementasinya*" Publisher: Mandar Maju" 2011
- [28.] Iksan M., *Administrasi Keuangan Publik*, Second Edition. Universitas Terbuka Tangerang Selatan, 2014
- [29.] Kadri Renggono, MSI, *Kepala Badan Keuangan dan Pengelolaan Aset Daerah Kota Yogyakarta dalam kegiatan Kuliah Umum Internasional Program for Law and Sharia (IPOLS)*, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta (UMY), 30 Desember 2017, <http://www.umy.ac.id/>(retrieved on 30 Nopember 2018)
- [30.] Jeddawi Murtir, *Implementasi Kebijakan Otonomi Daerah*, Kreasi Total Media, Yogyakarta 2008.
- [31.] Jurnal Ferdian Hadifarta, *Analisis Peningkatan Pelayanan Publik (Study Dinas Kependudukan dan Pencatatan Sipil Kabupaten Mesuji)* 2010
- [32.] Jurnal Endiwanto P. Pasaribu (2011) *Analisis Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kualitas Pelayanan Pada Kantor Kecamatan Banjar Baru Kabupaten Tulang Bawang Skripsi : Rida Indah Fariani* (2013)
- [33.] Lijan Poltak, Sinambela, 2017, *Reformasi Pelayanan Publik*, Bumi Aksara: Jakarta.